

Cross-sectoral collaboration for biodiversity conservation in Sweden: challenges and opportunities

Contributors: Sara Zaman, Viola Hakkarainen, Rory Taylor, Christopher M. Raymond, Romina Martin, Erik Andersson, Nicole Vikatmaa

Key messages

1. Recognizing and **supporting everyday collaborative skills and competences of civil servants, civil society, and private sector actors** is crucial for successful biodiversity actions.

2. **Mixtures of formal and informal networks** across sectors and moving between them can be an effective strategy for long-term conservation efforts.

3. Participatory spatial planning processes such as **geodesign can help coordinate biodiversity policy implementation** on the ground by promoting effective inter-municipal dialogue around landscape design problems.

Key terms and ideas

- **Inclusive conservation:** seeks to recognize plural values and visions of stakeholders in protected area management and biodiversity conservation (Raymond et al., 2022).
- **Socio-political fragmentation:** referring to the different levels of political support, the diversity of values and interests, and the differing ambitions and policy tools (Hakkarainen and Raymond, 2025).
- **Geodesign:** a participatory and iterative spatial planning method to evaluate landscape design proposals through geographic context, geospatial technology and systems thinking (Steinitz, 2012).

Introduction

The European Union's Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR) aims to restore degraded land and seas across Europe. Chapter three of the NRR notes that EU Member States, including Sweden, are to prepare national-level plans to implement restoration measures (Regulation (EU) 2024/1991, 2024). These plans must commit to synergizing efforts across relevant policy sectors, public consultation, and stakeholder engagement (European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, 2025). Simultaneously, actions to conserve and restore biodiversity are taken at the local level and greatly shaped by ongoing work in municipalities (McPhearson et al., 2023).

Achieving the goals of the NRR will require systemic and transformative change across governance levels and societal sectors. However, policy responses to curb biodiversity decline in Europe are so far insufficient (IPBES, 2019). The implementation of inclusive conservation is often constrained, marked by disconnections and power imbalances across sectors and governance levels (Raymond et al., 2022; Ulug et al., 2024). Ahead of Sweden's submission of a draft national restoration plan in 2026, it is vital to understand the potential roadblocks to cross-sectoral collaboration for biodiversity conservation, and to devise possible solutions at the local level across public and private sectors. This is particularly important in view of the collaborations that must occur over productive landscapes like agriculture and forestry areas.

In this brief, we explore how collaboration between public and private sectors can be strengthened to address biodiversity loss at the municipal and regional levels. The RECONNECT project has addressed these concerns by examining the synergies across institutional, ecological, and social dimensions of biodiversity conservation to overcome fragmentation across sectors. Based on studies conducted by RECONNECT in Sweden, we highlight **three Key Messages** that discuss challenges facing collaboration across land use and biodiversity conservation sectors and communications-based recommendations for overcoming them. We propose **geodesign as one concrete tool** for fostering collaboration among municipalities and with respective partners. These challenges and recommendations provide insights on municipal and regional implementation of the NRR.

Challenges and recommendations

Key Message 1

Recognizing and **supporting everyday collaborative skills and competences of civil servants, civil society, and private sector actors** is crucial for successful biodiversity actions.

Challenge

Researchers have indicated the importance of municipal-level civil servants and actors at the local level for addressing the implementation challenge of international biodiversity conservation agreements (Borgström, 2019; Phang et al., 2020). Municipal civil servants working on biodiversity issues operate within a complex political and organizational environment shaped by multiple values and often divergent interests. They work at the intersection of conflicting goals, such as urban and housing development and biodiversity conservation. They are also embedded in day-to-day governance and interpret, negotiate, and enact changes. However, their agency is constrained by narrow or limited policy instruments and data, weak organizational processes, unclear mandates, and a lack of shared competence on biodiversity and its many connections to society in their organizations.

Day-to-day practices are underutilized and underrecognized as a potential tool for policy implementation. For example, everyday practices such as the negotiation of development plans, formation of key relationships, building long-term, trusting partnerships, and interpersonal communication on the relevance of conservation and restoration are missing from high-level biodiversity targets.

Recommendation

The creation of place-based, inter-municipal learning spaces that support agreed-to standards for respectful and effective knowledge exchange would help to recognize day-to-day realities of local governance.

In our interviews with municipal civil servants, our results show that their work is enabled by several key factors.

- Supportive and mandated relationships within and beyond their organization
- Trust and credibility among colleagues and politicians cultivated through shared spaces
- Alignment with planning and decision-making cycles (“right timing”) via strategic agenda setting
- Personal capacities and competencies in continuous development such as an ability to listen and articulate convincingly
- Institutional continuity through accumulated and continuously shared experiences
- Institutional support for investing in shadow networks and relations that could be needed in the future

These enabling conditions illustrate that effective biodiversity governance depends as much on organizational culture and relationships as on formal structures or regulations (Hakkarainen and Raymond 2025). Our interviews with companies indicate how similar everyday capacities are also required in collaborations with the private sector and within it, where actors are often working under different mandates, incentives, and planning horizons. In these settings, diplomatic skills such as translating complex concepts, navigating conflicting priorities, and keeping actors engaged across organizational boundaries help to enable action.

Key message 2

Mixtures of formal and informal networks across public and private sectors and moving between them can be an effective strategy for long-term conservation efforts.

Challenge

A lack of clear mandates means that municipal-level policy implementation is often shaped by **informal or shifting collaborations**, which are based on short- to medium-term needs.

One of the core issues facing municipal-level biodiversity conservation is insufficient dedicated public funding to sustain continuous inter-municipal efforts lasting 5 or more years. While planning documents set expectations for long-term visions, short-term project-based funding is often distributed based on regional administrative capacity (Borgström et al., 2016). As a result, collaborations between ecologists across municipalities, or between departments within municipalities, are based on short-term needs. These collaborations do not have the ability to effectively plan, often finding themselves playing “catch-up” instead of implementing visions for conservation and restoration. The private sector faces comparable pressures, as time constraints, shifting reporting expectations, and limited capacity can push companies toward reactive, minimum-compliance behavior. Short planning cycles and regulatory ambiguity make it difficult for organizations to maintain long-term attention on biodiversity.

In our surveys with municipal biodiversity conservation and restoration experts, we have seen that there is also an uneven level of knowledge about ecology and biodiversity within and across municipalities. This leads to collaborations with diverse actors that must work together **as best as they can** to achieve concrete objectives. Similarly, in many companies biodiversity knowledge is also uneven, siloed or missing. These differences can make coordination difficult and point to the importance of networks that help build shared understanding across sectors.

Recommendation

Building long-term support and funding for diverse collaborative networks has potential for bridging the policy-implementation gap.

Past research shows that persuasive yet flexible long-term commitments towards conservation at the national level have helped provide touchstones for ongoing policy debates in the Netherlands (Beunen & Barba Lata, 2021). Long-term national commitments to support municipal-level conservation work through financial and personnel growth can expand prioritization from immediate needs and increase the agility of policy implementation. Additionally, long-term commitment from municipalities can help sustain grassroots initiatives (Borgström, 2019). In our survey research, we find that informal networks across municipalities, departments, and the public and private sector can support local, specific implementation of biodiversity conservation laws. We also find that formal networks in the private sector, such as Business & Biodiversity Sweden, offer structured spaces for shared learning and benchmarking. They help companies interpret emerging or shifting regulatory expectations and reduce uncertainty by allowing companies at different stages of biodiversity work to compare approaches. Our recommendation also supports the need for unambiguous municipal and regional mandates to clarify roles in conservation and restoration practices.

Key message 3

Participatory spatial planning processes such as geodesign can help coordinate biodiversity policy implementation on the ground by promoting effective inter-municipal dialogue around landscape design problems.

Challenge

Effective biodiversity policy implementation and action by municipal and regional actors remains constrained by **insufficient support and opportunities for deliberation**.

Recommendation

Deliberative geodesign processes that are representative, sustained and integrated into planning processes act as boundary spaces that **enable meaningful inter-municipal knowledge sharing**, co-learning and dialogue **for coordinated biodiversity policy implementation**.

Geodesign processes are iterative and deliberative. This **promotes shared learning between civil servants** as they collaborate to solve problems, develop design solutions and identify pathways to translate those solutions into action.

The facilitation of geodesign processes is critical. Three key items must be ensured:

1. **Ensure representation:** A geodesign project must ensure the relevant actors are involved (**including those with political power**), the right organizations are engaged, and right data are used to represent the landscape or issue of concern.
2. **Start early:** Relevant actors should be engaged consistently before the geodesign process begins, during its implementation and after it concludes.
3. **Balance:** An accurate reflection of the complexity of real-world biodiversity policy implementation must be balanced with the technical simplicity of the geodesign tool.

Landscape context

A situated Geodesign process

Solutions iteratively inform later geodesign process and larger planning context.

Image credit: Rory Taylor

Geodesign is a widely applied participatory spatial planning method involving the iterative creation and evaluation of landscape design proposals informed by geographic context, geospatial technology and systems thinking (Steinitz, 2012). Implementation involves the use of interactive digital mapping tools in group settings to examine shared planning issues, creatively and collectively design solutions to those issues, and by doing so, facilitate collaboration and boundary management among diverse actors (Gottwald et al., 2021; Pettit et al., 2019).

A geodesign process was implemented in November 2023 with civil servants from 7 municipalities in Greater Stockholm to collectively design landscape solutions to improve ecological connectivity across the Järvakilens green wedge. The geodesign process was a creative exercise of collaborative inter-municipal planning and design in a digital environment. While it produced connectivity design solutions that impart insights on planning for ecological connectivity across Järvakilens, its key value for conservation planning arose primarily through the process of collaboratively articulating, thinking through and deliberating over how to improve and secure ecological connectivity.

Geodesign outputs (e.g. designs or maps) are boundary objects that facilitate communication and knowledge exchange on local biodiversity conservation issues and management efforts between civil servants from different municipalities and with different expertise. A digital map interface enables multi-scale and dynamic engagement by civil servants with the landscape and conservation issues in spatially explicit ways. This encourages **dialogue over the challenges and nuances of planning for and implementing biodiversity policy at the local level.**

Conclusions

Through our Key Messages, we suggest that Sweden’s national-level draft proposal for the NRR include support for formal and informal collaborations at the municipal level and across sectors. Potential solutions derived from the RECONNECT project’s research show that this support can be managed through long-term investments in collaborative learning spaces. Additionally, we suggest that it will be crucial to build upon collaborative networks that already exist. Geodesign tools can be used as one possible space for knowledge sharing. This tool can strengthen over time as the demands of representation and co-design are implemented more regularly.

While this policy brief has focused on Sweden’s draft plan of the NRR, our recommendations are also likely to be salient for other Member States, as the NRR proposes that Member States find synergies across their national-level plans where possible. Overall, we find that the strategic approach of the NRR in support of transparent engagement with relevant stakeholders can be achieved through the long-term commitments and concrete tools highlighted above.

RECONNECT investigates the social-ecological relationships between protected areas and the larger landscapes that they are embedded in. The project explores ecological, social, and institutional connections to understand how protected areas relate to the ‘outside’ world. With this systemic take, the project goes beyond the conventional approach to biodiversity conservation and contributes to better coherence in discussions and decisions about the management of landscapes.

RECONNECT is 3-year long research project (2023-2026) sponsored by Biodiversa+ and the EU, with a budget of approximately 1,4 million Euros. It spans across four different case studies, namely Stockholm (Sweden), Göttingen (Germany), Grenoble (France), and Cape Town (South Africa). The partners are: Stockholm University, IUCN European Regional Office, French National Centre for Scientific Research, University of Helsinki, University of Göttingen, University of Western Cape and University of Cape Town.

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